

Fine-mapping of blast resistance genes.

scored as segregating. Similarly, each F_2 plant or F_3 family was given a score for each RFLP marker according to whether the F_2 was homozygous for the allele of the resistant parent (3), homozygous for the allele of the susceptible parent (1), or heterozygous (2). In cases where the RFLP pattern of the heterozygous stake was not easily distinguishable from the homozygous resistant stake (because of a null allele), a score of 4 was assigned.

Breeding methods

Restorers and maintainers identified for developing Basmati hybrids

A. K. Sarial, V. P. Singh, and F. U. Zaman, Genetics Division, Indian Agricultural Research Institute (IARI), New Delhi 110012, India

Linkage of donor alleles and resistance phenotype was confirmed by chi-square analysis. The genetic distances between markers and resistance genes were estimated using the computer program MAPMAKER (see figure).

As reported by previous workers, we also found RG64 to be closely linked with $Pi-2$ (t) on chromosome 6 and RG869 and RZ397 to be linked with $Pi-4$ (t) on chromosome 12. However, we found the

members to be closer to the target resistance genes in terms of map units than previously reported. We estimated RG64 to be 2.1 cM from $Pi-2$ (t), RG869 to be 5.4 cM, and RZ397 to be 3.3 cM away from $Pi-4$ (t). A new flanking marker, RG241, was identified to be 5.2 cM from $Pi-4$ (t). For $Pi-1$ (t), marker NpB181 was found to be more closely linked (3.5 cM) than RZ536 (11.4 cM). The shorter distances that we obtained may be attributed to the use of larger mapping population sizes (see table). With the identification and confirmation of these closely linked flanking markers to blast resistance genes, it is now possible to use these markers for marker-assisted breeding. Marker-assisted plant selection with these flanking markers is being used for pyramiding the three major blast resistance genes. ■

High volume expansion through linear kernel elongation, fluffiness, and appealing aroma and taste characterize Basmati rice. To develop acceptable Basmati hybrids, both parents must have these cooking and eating characteristics. Basmati germplasm restorers, however, have not been available.

We crossed 26 genotypes possessing Basmati grain and cooking characteristics

with four cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines: IR58025 A, IR62829 A, PMS10 A, and PMS3 A. Thirteen genotypes were selected based on pollen fertility. Crosses were repeated to confirm maintaining and restoring ability. Genotypes were categorized as effective restorers (> 80% spikelet fertility), partial restorers (21-79% spikelet fertility), and maintainers (< 1% spikelet fertility). ■

Table 1. Fertility restoration and sterility maintenance ability of improved Basmati genotypes.^a

Genotype	CMS line															
	IR58025 A			IR62829 A			PMS10 A			PMS3 A						
	Pollen fertility (%) ^{R^b}	Spikelet fertility (%) ^{Kh^c}	Category ^d	Pollen fertility (%) ^R	Spikelet fertility (%) ^{Kh}	Category	Pollen fertility (%) ^R	Spikelet fertility (%) ^{Kh}	Category	Pollen fertility (%) ^R	Spikelet fertility (%) ^{Kh}	Category				
Basmati 385	43.90	71.53	82.91	R	^e 64.42	69.07	PR	53.50	76.56	81.10	R	85.40	71.51	82.43	R	
Chandan	87.40	87.95	81.62	R	66.47	69.90	PR	37.80	60.25	79.17	R	90.25	81.00	80.14	R	
P1031-8-5-1-1	2.00	6.00	10.43	WM	91.00	80.55	R	52.00	82.84	79.96	R	61.70	92.80	78.85	R	
HKR241-IET-12020 S.A.F.	86.95	68.80	80.34	R	38.70	69.02	PR	71.20	64.50	80.29	R	63.15	60.00	80.60	R	
Khalsa 7	-	71.60	63.40	PR	87.24	60.21	PR	84.69	77.60	80.05	R	82.70	78.51	64.52	PR	
Karnal Local	92.47	73.87	81.15	R	74.13	69.70	PR	67.80	79.40	79.10	R	90.70	74.00	45.71	PR	
HKR46	83.80	70.17	78.82	R	59.90	72.40	60.08	PR	83.15	81.09	86.35	R	85.30	84.04	66.85	PR
P1173-2-1	72.60	43.62	4.83	PR	80.57	65.67	PR	81.05	61.00	53.82	PR	77.30	40.25	58.97	PR	
P1173-4-1	08.00	0.00	0.87	M	0.00	5.25	WM	0.00	0.00	0.47	M	09.00	0.00	0.67	M	
P615-K-167-13	27.20	0.00	3.71	WM	0.02	1.63	WM	-	0.00	0.00	M	23.30	1.00	0.00	M	
Hasan Sarai	55.00	45.00	49.08	PR	71.19	49.17	PR	43.70	63.50	26.90	PR	37.50	58.82	45.30	PR	
Basmati 370	-	0.00	0.00	M	0.00	0.00	M	-	0.00	0.00	M	-	0.00	0.00	M	
Pusa Basmati	10.00	0.00	0.00	M	0.00	0.00	M	0.00	0.00	0.00	M	0.00	0.00	0.00	M	

^aData pooled over 2 replications. ^bR = 1993 rabi (wet season). ^cKh = 1993 kharif (dry season). ^dR = restorer, PR = partial restorer, WM = weak maintainer, M = maintainer. ^e- = Crops not attempted because of nonsynchronization.

Table 2. Grain quality features of promising Basmati restorers and maintainers.^a

Genotype	Aroma ^b	Before cooking			After cooking				
		Grain length (mm)	Grain breadth (mm)	L-B ratio	Grain length (mm)	Grain breadth (mm)	L-B ratio	Elongation ratio	Alkali value
Basmati 385	1	6.6	1.7	3.9	11.9	2.7	4.4	1.8	4.0
Chandan	1	7.3	1.8	4.1	12.4	3.5	3.5	1.7	4.0
P1031-8-5-1-1	1	8.2	1.8	4.6	16.4	2.5	6.6	2.0	5.0
HKR241-IET-12020	1	7.5	1.7	4.4	12.8	3.0	4.3	1.7	4.0
S.A.F. Khalsa 7	1	7.4	1.8	4.1	15.6	2.6	6.0	2.1	4.0
Karnal Local	1	7.3	1.7	4.3	13.9	3.6	3.9	1.9	4.0
HKR46	2	5.5	1.7	3.2	8.3	1.9	4.4	1.5	6.0
P1173-2-1	1	5.5	1.7	3.2	8.3	2.4	3.5	1.5	1.0
P1173-4-1	2	5.5	1.7	3.2	8.8	2.8	3.1	1.6	1.0
P615-K-167-13	2	6.4	1.7	3.8	12.2	2.5	4.9	1.9	7.0
Hasan Sarai	2	0.7	1.8	4.5	12.1	1.9	6.4	1.8	4.0
Basmati 370	1	6.9	1.8	3.8	12.4	2.1	5.9	1.8	4.0
Pusa Basmati 1	2	7.2	1.8	4.0	14.4	2.2	6.5	2.0	6.0

^aData pooled over 2 replications. ^b1 = strong; 2 = moderate.

Basmati 385, Chandan, and HKR241-IET-12020 were found to be effective restorers for IR58025 A, PMS10 A, and PMS3 A; P1031-8-5-1-1 for IR62829 A, PMS10 A, and PMS3 A; Kamal Local and HKR46 for IR58025 A and PMS10

A, and S.A.F. Khalsa 7 for PMS10 A (Table 1).

Basmati 370 and Pusa Basmati 1 were found to be effective maintainers for the four CMS lines; P1173-4-1 for IR58025 A, PMS10 A, and PMS3 A; and P615-K-

167-13 for PMS10 A and PMS3 A.

The performance of the restorers varied with CMS line, location, and season of testing. The differential ability to restore fertility in the CMS lines, which all have the wild abortive (WA) cytotsterile system, could be because of the influence of the different nuclear backgrounds of the CMS lines.

Among the restorers, Basmati 385, Chandan, P1031-8-5-1-1, HKR241-IET-12020, S.A.F. Khalsa 7, and Karnal Local possess acceptable grain dimensions and desirable degree of aroma and volume expansion through linear kernel elongation (Table 2). Similarly, among the maintainers, P615-K-167-13, Pusa Basmati 1, and Basmati 370 have acceptable grain and cooking quality characteristics for Basmati rice. These genotypes will contribute to developing Basmati hybrids and provide restorers and maintainers with acceptable key Basmati quality characteristics. ■

Identifying maintainers and restorers for three cytoplasmic male sterile lines of rice

Yog Raj and M. P. Pandey, Plant Breeding and Genetics Department, G.B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology (GBPUAT), Pantnagar 263145; and A. Kumar, Genetics Division, Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi 110012, India

In hybrid rice breeding programs based on a cytoplasmic genetic male sterility system, identifying effective maintainers and restorers is important.

We crossed cytoplasmic male sterile lines (CMS) V20 A, Zhen Shan 97 A (ZS97 A), and IR46830 A, which all possess wild abortive (WA) cytoplasm, with 18 varieties and elite lines in a line × tester design at the Crop Research Centre, (CRC), GPUAT. The 54 hybrids and their parents were transplanted in two 3-m rows at 20- × 20-cm spacing during 1991 wet season (WS).

Five plants were randomly selected and used for analyzing pollen and spikelet fertility. About 10 spikelets, representing the upper, middle, and lower portions of half emerging panicles, were collected and squashed in 2.2% IKI stain to observe pollen fertility.

Fertility reaction^a of F₁ hybrids involving 3 CMS lines at CRC, Pantnagar, India. 1991 WS.

Variety/elite line	CMS line		
	V20 A	ZS97 A	IR46830 A
Narendra 118	PR	PR	PR
Kasturi	M	PM	M
UPR79-11	R	PR	R
N22	M	PR	PR
Rasi	PR	R	PM
Govind	R	R	PR
IR36	R	R	PR
UPR79-123	R	R	R
BG367-4	PM	PM	R
Pant Dhan 4	M	PR	PM
Sarju 52	R	PR	PM
Pusa 205	PR	PR	R
Suweon 294	R	PR	R
Suweon 325	R	R	R
Manhar	R	R	PM
Pusa 702	R	R	PM
Suweon 332	R	R	R
UPR231-28-1-2	R	PR	PR

^aR = restorer (60.100% pollen fertility, 80-100% spikelet fertility), PR = partial restorer (30.60% pollen fertility, 30.80% spikelet fertility), PM = partial maintainer (1.30% pollen and spikelet fertility), and M = maintainer (<1% pollen and spikelet fertility).

Restorers and maintainers identified were usually different for the three CMS lines (see table). Suweon 325, Suweon 332, and UPR79-123 consistently restored fertility of all the CMS lines. Some other restorers found promising were UPR79-11, Govind, IR36, Sarju 52, Suweon 294, Manhar, Pusa 702, and UPR231-28-1-2 for V20 A: Rasi, Govind, IR36, Manhar,

and Pusa 702 for ZS 97 A; and UPR79-11, BG367-4, Pusa 205, and Suweon 294 for IR46830 A. Maintainers identified were Kasturi, N22, and Pant Dhan 4 for V20 A and Kasturi for IR46830 A. The frequency of restorers (48.1 %) was higher than that of maintainers (7.4%). We are using the promising restorers and maintainers in a hybrid rice breeding program. ■